

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Sun, 23 Feb 2020 21:15:46 +0000
To: Cate Hankins
Subject: RE: Suggestion for VMMC Speaker at Interest 2020 Conference
Attachments: RE: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm - VMMC

Sounds good. Our earlier emails attached.

PK

From: Cate Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>
Sent: Friday, February 21, 2020 10:24 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Re: Suggestion for VMMC Speaker at Interest 2020 Conference

Hi Peter,
I can ask Jason Reed at jpiego what he thinks about a speaker – has to be a pan-African talk for sure. Will copy you in.
Thanks,
Cate

From: "Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]" <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Date: Friday, February 21, 2020 at 11:57 AM
To: Emmanuel Njeuhmeli (b)(6)
Subject: RE: Suggestion for VMMC Speaker at Interest 2020 Conference

Hi Emmanuel,
Truly sorry we'll miss you in Windhoek. Sounds like a jolly time (b)(6) I'll let you know what we do about a VMMC presentation and plans for next year's meeting.

Stay well,
PK

From: Emmanuel Njeuhmeli (b)(6)
Sent: Friday, February 21, 2020 9:32 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Re: Suggestion for VMMC Speaker at Interest 2020 Conference

Dear Peter,

Sorry for the late reply to your email, I was trying to look at my schedule and decide whether I will be able to attend or not the conference.

(b)(6)

So, I will not be able to attend this year. If I can support the conference in the future, please let me know, I would be glad to do so.

Best regards,
Emmanuel

On Tue, Feb 18, 2020 at 11:48 AM Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov> wrote:
Hi Emmanuel,
Are you still thinking of coming to the INTEREST meeting in Windhoek May 5-8? Could you speak about VMMC?

Thanks,
PK

From: Emmanuel Njeuhmeli <(b)(6)>
Sent: Thursday, December 19, 2019 10:23 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Suggestion for VMMC Speaker at Interest 2020 Conference

Dear Peter,

I want to suggest Valerian Kiggundu (vkiggundu@usaid.gov or (b)(6)) as the speaker for VMMC at Interest 2020 Conference.

Valerian is the VMMC Advisor at USAID Washington and before joining USAID, worked at Rakai Health Sciences Project in Rakai, Uganda with Ron Gray, and was the guys who did most the circumcisions during the Uganda VMMC RCT. He can very well speak of the progress in scaling up VMMC as well as the new research questions, issues, and challenges the program has.

Best regards,
Emmanuel

Emmanuel Njeuhmeli, MD, MPH, MBA

email: (b)(6)

Cell phone: (b)(6)

--

Best regards,

Emmanuel

Emmanuel Njeuhmeli, MD, MPH, MBA

email: (b)(6)

Cell phone: (b)(6)

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Thu, 19 Dec 2019 21:36:51 +0000
To: Catherine Hankins
Subject: RE: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm - VMMC

Hi Cate,
Emmanuel said he's (b)(6) I'm not sure who he is working with. He said he has work in Windhoek and may plan to attend the meeting. After he said that, I asked if he might also be interested in being a speaker (with no promises) and he said sure.

PK

From: Cate Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>
Sent: Thursday, December 19, 2019 3:58 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Re: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm - VMMC

Hi Peter,
That would be good if Emmanuel can be free but who would pay for him? When he (b)(6) did he eventually (b)(6)

Btw, agree about non-traditional circ being virtually anything (from a nick to loss of the penis).
As for older men, small numbers is the best possible explanation.

Thanks
Cate

C Hankins MD PhD FRCPC CM

(b)(6)

On Dec 19, 2019, at 15:21, Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov> wrote:

If we have just one, I'm told Dr. June is very good. Emmanuel is also great and could be a freebie if he is coming anyway. On the other hand, good to have new African faces. Could have a Emmanuel-June tag team, total 25 minutes?

PK

From: Cate Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>
Sent: Thursday, December 19, 2019 3:08 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Re: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm - VMMC

Hi Peter,

Good for you for taking them on – it is important to keep communications open even if they seem so adamant. Am not sure we can have more than one VMMC talk. I am worried about Guido having a full basic science hour. Figure that we have 19 talks of 25 minutes and one debate. The sponsors are slow in declaring. Tigi is a very good speaker. Have known Emmanuel for years and years. What do you think?

All the best,

Cate

From: "Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]" <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Date: Thursday, December 19, 2019 at 2:11 PM

To: Catherine Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>

Subject: FW: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm - VMMC

Hi Cate,

I asked Emmanuel Njeuhmeli, Carlos Toledo (VMMC lead at CDC), and Amy Herman-Roloff (CDC Director, South Africa) for suggestions on VMMC speakers.

1. Emmanuel may be coming to Windhoek and could speak again, especially if we have more than one speaker.
2. I'm told either of these two would be great. Dr. June is more scientific. Tigi is a better speaker and more applied.
 - a. Elijah Odoyo-June (CDC-Kenya office)
 - b. Tigistu "Tigi" Adamu Ashengo (formerly JHPIEGO, now working in Ethiopia)

Note: The attached poster from the PHIA's shows that traditional circumcision and VMMC in older men were NOT protective. I was told: "Regarding non-medical MC, it's probably because it's many different things. In some places it's basically a slit, in others a semi circumcision, and in others a full circumcision. It really varies country to country and even within one country. For older men, we think there just wasn't enough power in the analysis as the findings were not significant. Incidence is just a very rare event to capture in these cross sectional surveys. And we know that MC coverage in men >35 is fairly low in most countries." Still some interesting science! BTW - I've been "debating" with some intactivists on Twitter.

Please let me know if you want to proceed and whether to think about one, two, or three speakers.

Thanks,

PK

From: Cate Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>

Sent: Wednesday, December 4, 2019 8:32 PM

Cc: Marloes Nijboer <m.nijboer@aighd.org>

Subject: Save the time: Friday December 13 from 1300-1400 Amsterdam time 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm

Hi everyone,

Thank you for your quick replies and for the excellent ideas that have been coming in for the scientific programme and potential peer reviewers. Please mark this time in your calendars now: Friday December 13 from 1300-1400 Amsterdam time.

We will likely have the call by Zoom – Marloes will send the details.

If you haven't sent in ideas yet, please send in some priority subjects this week to add to the compilation that we will send out before the call. If you are unable to join the call, it would be good to get your ideas to share with others on the call, even if you can't join.

All the best,
Cate

From: Catherine Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>
Date: Sunday, December 1, 2019 at 11:07 PM
Cc: Marloes Nijboer <m.nijboer@aighd.org>
Subject: 2020 INTEREST Scientific Programme brainstorm

Hi everyone,

Hope that this finds you all well on World AIDS Day! Thank you for expressing your interest in continuing as an active member of the International Conference Committee (ICC) for INTEREST 2020! Your suggestions for new peer reviewers have been welcome – please do keep sending more along with contact info.

It is time for us to brainstorm on potential topics for the scientific programme for INTEREST 2020. We have received some ideas so far (thank you!) and we have had some initial calls with sponsors about their topics.

Please answer the doodle poll and select all times (Dec 6-13) that are currently available for you. The poll will close this Wednesday night December 4th so that you can free up the other times.

(b)(6)

Please send your ideas for burning issues that you think INTEREST 2020 should cover and we will compile them for our discussion.

Looking forward to our first call!
All the best,
Cate

From: Catherine Hankins <c.hankins@aighd.org>

Date: Wednesday, October 23, 2019 at 6:59 PM

Subject: Looking forward to INTEREST 2020

Dear Members of the INTEREST 2019 International Conference Committee (ICC),

How are you? I hope this finds you well as we edge toward November. We are beginning work now on INTEREST 2020 which will be held May 5-8th 2020 in Windhoek, Namibia. This location edged out the three top choices that we considered at the ICC/EG/Sponsor lunch meeting in May during the 2019 INTEREST conference in Accra, Ghana.

In what we hope will become a tradition, following the attention that has been building before and after the February 9 Lancet theme issue on advancing women in science, medicine, and global health ([https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/issue/vol393no10171/PIIS0140-6736\(19\)X0006-9](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/issue/vol393no10171/PIIS0140-6736(19)X0006-9)), we have two Local Co-Chairs for INTEREST 2020. We warmly welcome Anne-Marie Nitscke, who is Director of Special Programmes (HIV, TB, Leprosy, Malaria, and Research Development) at the Ministry of Health and Social Services, and Ismael Katjitae, an internist who is Chair of the Ministry's HIV Technical Advisory Committee.

They will work with Professor Elly Katabira, who has agreed to stay on as a Co-Chair for another year, and myself as Scientific Chair. An invitation to the First Lady of Namibia, UNAIDS Special Advocate for young women and adolescent girls, to open the conference has been accepted. <https://www.unaids.org/en/aboutunaids/unaidsembassadors/MonicaGeingos>

After the 2018 INTEREST conference in Kigali, we formed the active International Conference Committee and the Emeritus Group composed of those who wanted to remain linked to INTEREST in a less active but nonetheless supportive role. Emeritus Group members are natural ambassadors for INTEREST, keeping an eye open for synergies and funding opportunities while continuing to promote INTEREST's early-career capacity building objectives in Africa. Some Emeritus Group members reviewed scientific abstracts, which was very much appreciated given the huge volume of abstracts submitted for INTEREST 2019. We accepted 435 abstracts from among the 613 that we received.

So today, there are two requests for you to consider:

1. Will you stay on the active ICC or join the Emeritus Group? Being an active ICC member means reviewing 60-100 abstracts on average, participating in email exchanges and conference calls about the scientific programme, taking on responsibility for organising one or more specific elements of the programme, and seeking out funding to participate actively in the actual meeting. INTEREST can help you with some costs but if you attend INTEREST 2019 you will likely need to co-fund your participation to a certain level.
2. Whether you remain an ICC member or not, we need help to identify early and mid-career researchers to begin to engage with the INTEREST process. This year I would

propose that we start first by asking all 4 Joep Lange award recipients (2016-2019) to review abstracts for us in their chosen fields. In addition, could you please consider nominating someone as a reviewer? It could also be someone you would like to be considered already for the ICC should you be moving to the Emeritus Group or someone we should keep on our radar for the future. In any case, we need more scientific peer reviewers!

Please get back to me should you have any questions or concerns. Please indicate the role that most suits you at this time, along with any comments that can help us in the final composition of the Emeritus Group and the active committee.

ICC Active committee

Yes: _____

No: _____

Comments: _____

Emeritus Group:

Yes: _____

No: _____

Comments: _____

Suggestions for additional reviewers:

It would be appreciated if you could reply in the next week or so before we reach November.

Thank you to each and every one of you for making INTEREST what it has become today!

All the best,

Cate

Catherine Hankins MD PhD FRCPC CM

Scientific Chair, INTEREST 2020, May 5-8, Windhoek, Namibia

Deputy Director, Science; Amsterdam Institute for Global Health and Development; Department of Global Health, Academic Medical Center, University of Amsterdam

Professor of Public and Population Health, Department of Epidemiology, Biostatistics, and Occupational Health, Faculty of Medicine, McGill University, Montreal

Honorary Professor, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology, Faculty of Epidemiology and Population Health, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

c.hankins@aighd.org; catherine.hankins@mcgill.ca; catherine.hankins@lshtm.ac.uk

(b)(6)

From: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 20 Dec 2019 15:51:58 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Subject: RE: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Definitely. And Dr. June is more eloquent than I can ever hope to be.

C

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Friday, December 20, 2019 10:50 AM
To: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

OK, thanks Carlos. I'm told we'll probably just have one speaker on VMMC, so will prioritize the Africans.

Best,
PK

From: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>
Sent: Friday, December 20, 2019 10:38 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: RE: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Thanks Peter.

I wasn't planning to go to the meeting. We've been working on that one abstract...but otherwise not opposed to potentially speaking. We just have the restrictions for conferences.

b)(5)

C

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Thursday, December 19, 2019 2:07 PM
To: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Thanks a lot Carlos.

Are you thinking of coming to the Windhoek meeting (and potentially interested in speaking)?

I'm confused about "incidence difference." Was adjusted incidence in older VMMC men higher or lower than in uncircumcised men?

Best,
PK

From: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>
Sent: Thursday, December 19, 2019 10:27 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: RE: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Yes, publication will hopefully be out in a special issue for PHIA. It was presented at ICASA...here's the poster. Yes, we controlled for all that plus community viral load in women.

(b)(5)

Hope that helps. Let me know if you have any other questions.

C

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Monday, December 16, 2019 5:17 PM
To: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Hi again Carlos. Here's an email string about MC in PHIA.

Are the data going to be presented soon? Any clues why traditional circumcision and circumcision in older men were not protective? Are those results of multivariable analysis accounting for age, sexual behavior, etc.

Thanks for any insight.

PK

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Monday, November 25, 2019 6:59 AM
To: Rogers, John H. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <yet6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Gonese, Elizabeth (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <hol9@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Thanks John. I'll be eager to see it when published. Is it going to be presented at a conference? Any theories as to why traditional circumcision and circumcision in older men are not protective? I assume these are results of multivariable analysis accounting for age, sexual behavior, etc.

Don't worry, I'm not going to tweet anything without a reference.

Thanks,
PK

Peter Kilmarx
Fogarty International Center

On Nov 25, 2019, at 01:23, Rogers, John H. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <yet6@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Peter-

It's nice to hear from you! There is a multicountry PHIA paper in clearance now that examines HIV incidence by circumcision status. Quickly, ^{(b)(5)}

(b)(5)

As these statements are not yet cleared, I'd appreciate your discretion in Twitter and other fora. Let me know what other questions you have. I'm happy to share what I can.

Best,

John

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Sent: Friday, November 22, 2019 6:27 PM

To: Gonese, Elizabeth (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <hol9@cdc.gov>; Rogers, John H. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <yet6@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

+ John

Thanks Elizabeth. I'd potentially interested. A few things to consider:

1. Should this be an analysis focused on circumcision, or look at all risk factors for HIV infection, one of which will be circumcision?
2. Incident, prevalent, or both?
3. Zimbabwe only, or combine multiple countries? Obviously a multi-country analysis would need a discussion with Atlanta and ICAP.

What do you think?

Peter Kilmarx
Fogarty International Center

On Nov 22, 2019, at 02:03, Gonese, Elizabeth (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <hol9@cdc.gov> wrote:

Dear Peter

The PHIA data has not been analysed. These guys are definitely referring to DHS - which unfortunately the circumcision question was not relating to strictly medical circumcision

If you are interested in writing that up, we can let John Rogers know by way on short concept note.

Sorry for delay in response. (b)(6)

Regards

E. Gonese

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From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Tuesday, November 19, 2019 7:44:48 PM
To: Gonese, Elizabeth (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <hol9@cdc.gov>
Subject: ZIMPHIA and VMMC

Hi Elizabeth,

Greetings from Bethesda! I'm in a small Twitter war with some anti-circumcision "intactivists." They are claiming that data show that MC not protective in Zimbabwe, maybe from old DHS data? I looked at the ZIMPHIA results online and calculated that HIV infection was 7.0% in circumcised and 14.8% in uncircumcised, 57% lower odds in circumcised. Has this been analyzed and reported elsewhere either for Zimbabwe or across all the PHIA's?

Thanks and best wishes,
PK

Peter H. Kilmarx, MD, FACP, FIDSA
Rear Admiral, U.S. Public Health Service
Deputy Director, Fogarty International Center
U.S. National Institutes of Health

Cell (b)(6) Tel: +1-301-496-1415

Email peter.kilmarx@nih.gov

<[image001.jpg](#)>

<[image002.png](#)>

<[image003.png](#)>

Impact · Integrity · Innovation

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Fri, 9 Aug 2019 10:36:54 +0000
To: Nuno Gaspar
Subject: Re: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete

Thanks Nuno.

On Aug 9, 2019, at 4:51 AM, Nuno Gaspar <ngaspar@usaid.gov> wrote:

Hi all,

Apologies for not responding sooner but I have been out in the field.
We will revert to you soon on this.

Best,

N

Enviado do meu iPhone

No dia 09/08/2019, às 09:08, Shannon Young <shyoung@usaid.gov> escreveu:

Hi Nuno - just checking in to see if you were able to respond to this request for information.

Best,

Shannon Young
Division Chief - HIV/AIDS & TB
Integrated Health Office
U.S. Agency for International Development - Mozambique

Mobile: (b)(6)
Office: +258 2135 2097

----- Forwarded message -----

From: **Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)** <vrm9@cdc.gov>
Date: Mon, Jul 29, 2019 at 11:26 AM
Subject: RE: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>, Singer, Daniel (Dan) (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHP) <dps4@cdc.gov>, Greenberg, Seth <sgreenberg@usaid.gov>, shyoung@usaid.gov <shyoung@usaid.gov>
Cc: Nuno Gaspar <ngaspar@usaid.gov>

Thanks, Dan and Peter.

I have included Nuno Gaspar who is the VMMC POC at USAID and may assist on providing the VMMC data from Tete province.

Best,

Inacio

Inácio D. Malimane, MD

Prevention Deputy Branch Chief

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

(b)(6) cell | IMalimane@cdc.gov

+258 21 31 4747/48 office | +258 21 31 44 60 fax

7th Floor, JAT Complex 4, Av. 267 Zedequias Manganhela

Maputo, Mozambique

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Sent: Sunday, July 28, 2019 2:20 PM

To: Singer, Daniel (Dan) (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHP) <dps4@cdc.gov>; Greenberg, Seth <sgreenberg@usaid.gov>; Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <vrm9@cdc.gov>; shyoung@usaid.gov

Subject: RE: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete

Hi all and thanks in advance for any information. Dan describes the question well. It would be surprising if the province with the lowest prevalence of MC has the lowest prevalence of HIV. I'm told the MC estimates may be inaccurate and there is actually a lot of traditional MC.

Thanks,
PK

From: Singer, Daniel (Dan) (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHP) <dps4@cdc.gov>

Sent: Saturday, July 27, 2019 10:53 PM

To: Greenberg, Seth <sgreenberg@usaid.gov>; Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <vrm9@cdc.gov>; shyoung@usaid.gov

Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Subject: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete

Shannon, Seth, and Inacio,

Peter Kilmarx (cc'd) is the deputy director of the Fogarty International Center at NIH. He wrote to me inquiring on why the HIV prevalence in Tete is so low when the VMMC rate there is also low. As you know, there is a small group of people who think that male circumcision is immoral or abusive, and they are (apparently) making the argument that Tete proves VMMC is not necessary to control HIV.

Peter can clarify/correct the details of the discussion, but he is very interested in understanding what really drives the HIV epidemic in Tete and whether there is any truth to this apparent disparity. Could you provide him updated data and some context to help in a very difficult back-and-forth with some "intactivists"?

Please loop in anyone else appropriate from your teams.

And warm regards from Almaty.

Dan

Daniel A. Singer, MD, MPH, FACP
Regional Director for Central Asia
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention -
Almaty
E-mail: dsinger@cdc.gov

Enviado do meu iPhone

No dia 29/07/2019, às 11:26, Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <vrm9@cdc.gov> escreveu:

Thanks, Dan and Peter.

I have included Nuno Gaspar who is the VMMC POC at USAID and may assist on providing the VMMC data from Tete province.

Best,

Inacio

Inácio D. Malimane, MD

Prevention Deputy Branch Chief

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

(b)(6) cell | IMalimane@cdc.gov

+258 21 31 4747/48 office | +258 21 31 44 60 fax

7th Floor, JAT Complex 4, Av. 267 Zedequias Manganhela

Maputo, Mozambique

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Sent: Sunday, July 28, 2019 2:20 PM

To: Singer, Daniel (Dan) (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHP) <dps4@cdc.gov>; Greenberg, Seth <sgreenberg@usaid.gov>; Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <vrm9@cdc.gov>;

shyoung@usaid.gov

Subject: RE: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete

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From: Singer, Daniel (Dan) (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHP) <dps4@cdc.gov>

Sent: Saturday, July 27, 2019 10:53 PM

To: Greenberg, Seth <sgreenberg@usaid.gov>; Malimane, Inacio (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <vrm9@cdc.gov>; shyoung@usaid.gov

Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>

Subject: VMMC and HIV prevalence in Tete

Shannon, Seth, and Inacio,

Peter Kilmarx (cc'd) is the deputy director of the Fogarty International Center at NIH. He wrote to me inquiring on why the HIV prevalence in Tete is so low when the VMMC rate there is also low. As you know, there is a small group of people who think that male circumcision is immoral or abusive, and they are (apparently) making the argument that Tete proves VMMC is not necessary to control HIV.

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Please loop in anyone else appropriate from your teams.

And warm regards from Almaty.

Dan

Daniel A. Singer, MD, MPH, FACP
Regional Director for Central Asia
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention - Almaty
E-mail: dsinger@cdc.gov

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Wed, 1 May 2019 22:03:14 +0000
To: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: lecture at ECCMID

They aren't scientists. They say all kinds of terrible things about me!

From: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <sab0@cdc.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, May 1, 2019 5:57 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: Re: lecture at ECCMID

Oh no. I looked at their website, and that very article flashed across their screen, likely their most cited.

<https://www.jctres.com/en/about-jctr/>

Well that journal is not listed in DOAJ.org, which is

https://doaj.org/search?source=%7B%22query%22%3A%7B%22filtered%22%3A%7B%22filter%22%3A%7B%22bool%22%3A%7B%22must%22%3A%5B%7B%22term%22%3A%7B%22type%22%3A%22journal%22%7D%7D%5D%7D%7D%2C%22query%22%3A%7B%22query_string%22%3A%7B%22query%22%3A%22journal%20of%20clinical%20and%20translational%20research%22%2C%22default_operator%22%3A%22AND%22%7D%7D%7D%7D%2C%22from%22%3A0%2C%22size%22%3A10%7D

and yet there are 80 articles from that journal in PMC, with over a dozen NIH funded studies.

UGH!

BioRxiv has no indexing function but the initial screen is supposed to weed out pseudoscience. What did they say when you challenged them?

Sharon

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, May 1, 2019 5:47 PM
To: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT); Glass, Roger (NIH/FIC) [E]
Subject: RE: FYI my awesome lecture at ECCMID

Good for CDC!

A comment on bioRxiv. I had a little back and forth a while ago with some anti-circumcision "intactivists" promoting a "peer reviewed" paper in bioRxiv with an ecological analysis showing a link between male infant circumcision and SIDS. The paper was then published in J Clin Transl Res, "indexed in PubMed." ☺

Cheers,
PK

From: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <sab0@cdc.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, May 1, 2019 5:29 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>; Glass, Roger (NIH/FIC) [E] <glassr@mail.nih.gov>
Subject: Re: FYI my awesome lecture at ECCMID

Thanks, I'll make it more lively with questions when I give it again in 2 weeks to the Division of Lab sciences. It was tough to squeeze all that into 15

I hear

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, May 1, 2019 1:34:16 PM
To: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT); Glass, Roger (NIH/FIC) [E]
Cc: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: FYI my awesome lecture at ECCMID

Thanks Sharon – very informative! Information I will use.

All the best,
PK

From: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <sab0@cdc.gov>
Sent: Thursday, April 25, 2019 4:31 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>; Glass, Roger (NIH/FIC) [E] <glassr@mail.nih.gov>
Cc: Bloom, Sharon (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <sab0@CDC.GOV>
Subject: FYI my awesome lecture at ECCMID

Dear Peter and Roger

Here's a webcast of my 15-minute lecture in Amsterdam last weekend, at the European ID meetings (13K attendees). It was pretty rad, so I hope you listen to it and let me know your thoughts.

<https://www.eccmidlive.org/#!resources/journal-selection-changing-options-and-risks-for-authors-seeking-to-publish>

At a larger educational session with journal editors
<https://www.eccmidlive.org/#!contentsessions/36205>

THanks for listening, Sharon

Sharon Bloom MD
Executive Associate Editor
Emerging Infectious Diseases
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
sbloom@cdc.gov

(b)(6)

From: KRETSINGER, Katrina
Sent: Tue, 11 Dec 2018 13:14:52 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Subject: Re: Items on Male Circumcision, 2018 to Date

Great - please do!

Sent from my iPhone

On 11 Dec 2018, at 13:28, Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov> wrote:

Thanks Katrina. I am pretty happy with the progress being made with VMMC for HIV prevention in Africa, although it seems underemphasized relative to other prevention modalities. I still occasionally get tweeted at by intactivists. A luta continua!

I'll be (b)(6) and will get in touch.

Stay well,
PK

On Dec 10, 2018, at 11:50 PM, KRETSINGER, Katrina <kretsingerk@who.int> wrote:

Not sure who might be the best audience for this anymore, but thought you might! Cheers,
Katrina

Sent from my iPhone

Peter Kilmarx
Fogarty International Center, NIH

Begin forwarded message:

Resent-From: <kok4@cdc.gov>
From: Kaguimah Anthony <info@childmortality-prevention.org>
Date: 11 December 2018 at 00:56:19 CET
To: kok4@cdc.gov
Subject: **Items on Male Circumcision, 2018 to Date**

Items on Male
Circumcision,
2018 to Date

Items on Male Circumcision, 2018 to Date

Please see below, ranked by viewership, items on male circumcision to appear on www.childsurvival.net in 2018. While most items are from Africa, there are also items from Indonesia (item 1), Papua New Guinea (10), Texas (12), Thailand (13), Poland (16), and China (17).

Good reading.

Article Title	No of Hits
1. Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision to Prevent HIV in Tanah Papua, Indonesia: Field Trial to Assess Acceptability and Feasibility. http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7400	41
2. What device would be best for early infant male circumcision in east and southern Africa? Provider experiences and opinions with three different devices in Kenya. http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7007	38
3. Acceptability and feasibility of early infant male circumcision for HIV prevention in Malawi http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7005	36
4. Scale-Up of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision Services for HIV Prevention - 12 Countries in Southern and Eastern Africa, 2013-2016. http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=6998	34
5. Effect of male circumcision on risk of sexually transmitted infections and cervical cancer in women http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7001	33

6. Obtaining a male circumcision prevalence rate of 80% among adults in a short time: An observational prospective intervention study in the Orange Farm township of South Africa	32
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7008	
7. Use of the ShangRing circumcision device in boys below 18 years old in Kenya: results from a pilot study.	30
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7003	
8. Evidence that promotion of male circumcision did not lead to sexual risk compensation in prioritized Sub-Saharan countries	30
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7004	
9. Geographic Coverage of Male Circumcision in Western Kenya	30
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7009	
10. Re-establishing safer medical-circumcision-integrated initiation ceremonies for HIV prevention in a rural setting in Papua New Guinea. A multi-method acceptability study.	30
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7401	
11. CDC Male Circumcision Recommendations Represent a Key Public Health Measure	29
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7006	
12. Why are we cutting? A Survey of Cultural Views on Circumcision in the Texas Panhandle	29
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7397	
13. Physicians' and nurses' thoughts and concerns about introducing neonatal male circumcision in Thailand: a qualitative study.	29
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7398	
14. Modifying the health system to maximize voluntary medical male circumcision uptake: a qualitative study in Botswana	28
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=6997	
15. [Post-circumcision] Tetanus in adult males, Bugando Medical Centre, United Republic of Tanzania	27
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7000	
16. Attitudes, Beliefs and Predictors of Male Circumcision Promotion among Medical University Students in a Traditionally Non-Circumcising Region. [Poland]	27
http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7399	

17. Impact of Educational Interventions on Acceptance and Uptake of Male Circumcision in the General Population of Western China: A Multicenter Cohort Study. 27

http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7402

18. Predictors of voluntary medical male circumcision prevalence among men aged 25-39 years in Nyanza region, Kenya: Results from the baseline survey of the TASC0 study. 26

http://www.childsurvival.net/?content=com_articles&artid=7002

A small, light gray rectangular box containing the text '<powerphplist.png>'. This appears to be a broken image link or a placeholder for a logo.

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This message was sent to kok4@cdc.gov by info@childsurvival.net

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From: Brian Morris
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 10:18:43 +1000
To: Brian Morris
Subject: Male circ pubs this week: Nurse practitioners; Anesthesia (DPNB vs. EMLA); VMMC adverse events in Zimbabwe

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30185376>

J Pediatr Urol. 2018 Aug 6. pii: S1477-5131(18)30432-7. doi: 10.1016/j.jpurol.2018.07.027.

[Epub ahead of print]

Pediatric penile surgery by a nurse practitioner in the operating room.

Giramonti KM¹, Kogan BA².

Author information

1 Albany Medical Center Division of Urology, 23 Hackett Blvd, Albany, NY, 12208, USA.

Electronic address: giramok@amc.edu.

2 Albany Medical Center Division of Urology, 23 Hackett Blvd, Albany, NY, 12208, USA.

Electronic address: kogan@amc.edu.

Abstract

INTRODUCTION:

With the growing shortage of pediatric urological surgeons, it was our aim to streamline our system to get patients with less complex penile procedures performed in a timely manner. To do this, an advanced practice provider (APP) was trained to perform minor penile procedures in children in the operating room(OR).

OBJECTIVES:

The goal of our study was to show that with proper training an APP could safely perform a circumcision in the OR.

STUDY DESIGN:

After approval of the study center's credentialing committee, a NP was trained to perform revisions and initial circumcisions in children in the OR. The process involved: (1) observation, (2) first assisting and (3) performing the procedure with direct, and later in-direct, supervision. The first 100 cases were evaluated for surgical complications, post-operative complications and return rates to the OR.

RESULTS:

100 independent cases were completed with 90 having only in-direct supervision. There were no operative complications, nor any documented emergency room or urgent care visits in the immediate post-operative period. There were no early returns to the OR and only 1 scheduled follow-up procedure for a penile skin bridge.

DISCUSSION:

It was demonstrated that with proper training a NP can safely perform minor penile procedures in the OR. This allows us to free up our pediatric urology physicians to see and operate on more complex pediatric urology problems. In addition, it allows those with minor penile issues to be cared for more expeditiously. A concern related to training NPs to do circumcisions could be the

loss of control by urologists. In this situation, the attending physician is ultimately responsible from a medico-legal standpoint. That would not be true if the NP was practicing independently. With a shortage of urologists, this significantly expands the ability to care for our patient population. In addition, attending surgeons will have a greater freedom to perform major procedures. A limitation of the study was that a patient satisfaction survey was not obtained to see if there were concerns over a APP doing their circumcision. Personal feedback on 30 of the patients that did not return for the follow-up visit was not obtained. The authors of the study are primary providers of pediatric urology care in the study region, thus any individual with concerns would have been referred.

CONCLUSIONS:

It was demonstrated that a well-trained APP can safely perform minor penile procedures independently in the OR with indirect supervision.

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KEYWORDS:

Advanced practice provider; Circumcision; Nurse practitioner; Penile surgery

PMID: 30185376

DOI: [10.1016/j.jpuro.2018.07.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpuro.2018.07.027)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30188927>

PLoS One. 2018 Sep 6;13(9):e0203439. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0203439. eCollection 2018.

Dorsal penile nerve block versus eutectic mixture of local anesthetics cream for pain relief in infants during circumcision: A meta-analysis.

Wang J¹, Zhao S¹, Luo L¹, Liu Y¹, Zhu Z¹, Li E², Zhao Z¹.

Author information

1 Department of Urology & Andrology, Minimally Invasive Surgery Center, Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Urology, The First Affiliated Hospital of GuangZhou Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong, China.

2 Research Lab for Clinical & Translational Medicine, Medical School, University of South China; Hengyang, China.

Abstract

OBJECTIVE:

To compare dorsal penile nerve block (DPNB) and eutectic mixture of local anesthetics (EMLA) cream for pain relief in infants during circumcision.

METHODS:

We systematically searched Medline via PubMed, Embase, CNKI and the Cochrane Library Center Register to identify randomized controlled trials up to March 2018. Effect estimates were performed in random effect models. Mean neonate infant pain scale (NIPS) scores, incidence of hematoma, edema and erythema, mean heart rate were conducted to assessed the effect of analgesia. We found that the EMLA had significantly higher pain scores compared to DPNB (SMD = 3.72, 95% CI 1.27-6.17, P = 0.003). In DPNB group, the incidence of hematoma was significantly higher than EMLA group, OR = 0.03, 95% CI 0.00-0.24, P = 0.001. The analysis did not show any significant differences in mean heart rate and the risk of edema and erythema

between EMLA and DPNB group (SMD = 21.71, 95% CI = -0.88-44.30, P = 0.06 & OR = 0.40, 95% CI 0.15-1.07, P = 0.07 & OR = 7.33, 95% CI 0.84-64.07, P = 0.07).

CONCLUSION:

Based on the pooled results from the included studies, we found that DPNB was significantly more effective in pain relief as indicated by mean NIPS score than EMLA in infants during circumcision. However, use of DPNB significantly increased the risk of hematoma.

PMID: 30188927

DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0203439](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203439)

[Free full text](#)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30192816>

PLoS One. 2018 Sep 7;13(9):e0203292. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0203292. eCollection 2018.

Timing of adverse events among voluntary medical male circumcision clients: Implications from routine service delivery in Zimbabwe.

Feldacker C^{1,2}, Bochner AF^{1,3}, Murenje V⁴, Makunike-Chikwinya B⁴, Holec M¹, Xaba S⁵, Balachandra S⁶, Mandisarisa J⁶, Sidile-Chitimbire V⁷, Barnhart S^{1,2,8}, Tshimanga M⁹.

Author information

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2 Department of Global Health, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington, United States of America.

3 Department of Epidemiology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington, United States of America.

4 International Training and Education Center for Health (I-TECH), Harare, Zimbabwe.

5 Ministry of Health and Child Care, Harare, Zimbabwe.

6 U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Harare, Zimbabwe.

7 Zimbabwe Association of Church-related Hospitals (ZACH), Harare, Zimbabwe.

8 Department of Medicine, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington, United States of America.

9 Community Health Intervention Project (ZiCHIRe), Harare, Zimbabwe.

Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Timing of routine follow-up visits after adult male circumcision (MC) differs by country and method. Most men do not attend all routine follow-up visits. This cross-sectional study aimed to further understanding of AE timing within a large-scale, routine, MC program to improve patient safety.

METHODS:

From 2013-2017, ZAZIC consortium performed 192,575 MCs in Zimbabwe; the reported adverse event (AE) rate was 0.3%. Three scheduled, routine, follow-up visits intend to identify AEs. For surgical MC, visits were days 2, 7 and 42 post-procedure. For PrePex (device-based), visits were days 7, 14 and 49. Descriptive statistics explored characteristics of those patients with AEs. For each MC method, chi-square tests were used to evaluate associations between AE timing (days from MC to AE diagnosis) and factors of interest (age, AE type, severity).

RESULTS:

Of 421 AEs, 290 (69%) were surgical clients: 55 (19%) AEs were ≤2 days post-MC; 169 (58%) between 3-7 days; 47 (16%) between days 8-14; and 19 (7%) were ≥15 post-MC. Among surgical clients, bleeding was most common AE on/before Day 2 while infections predominated in other follow-up periods ($p < 0.001$). Younger surgical MC patients with AEs experienced AEs later than older clients ($p < 0.001$). Among 131 (31%) PrePex clients with AEs, 46 (35%) were ≤2 days post-MC; 59 (45%) between 3-7 days; 16 (12%) between days 8-14; and 10 (7%) ≥15 post-MC. For PrePex clients, device displacements were more likely to occur early while late AEs were most commonly infections ($p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSION:

Almost 23% of surgical and 8% of PrePex AEs occurred after Visit 2. Later AEs were likely infections. Clinicians, clients, and caregivers should be more effectively counseled that complications may arise after initial visits. Messages emphasizing attention to wound care until complete healing could help ensure client safety. Younger boys, ages 10-14, and their caregivers would benefit from improved, targeted, post-operative counseling.

PMID: 30192816

DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0203292](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203292)

[Free full text](#)

The following is an interesting article by the BBC. Could this also apply to intactivism? [With thanks to Chris Eley in the UK for his alert to this article.]

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-us-canada-45294192>

Russia trolls 'spreading vaccination misinformation' to create discord

Circumcision Academy of Australia: <https://www.circumcisionaustralia.info>

Circumcision Academy of Australia: <http://www.circumcisionaustralia.org>

Circumcision Academy of America: <http://www.circumcisionamerica.org>

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Australia

Brian J. Morris, AM DSc PhD FAHA

Professor Emeritus

School of Medical Sciences and Bosch Institute

Anderson Stuart Building (F13)

Sydney Medical School

The University of Sydney

Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

The contents of this email might include material that could possibly reflect the expert views of an academic at the University of Sydney. Unless stated otherwise they should not be regarded as representing University policy since on many issues that academic staff are expert in the University does not maintain any specific policy.

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Fri, 31 Aug 2018 14:15:00 +0000
To: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Good News!

Still getting this: <https://twitter.com/Intaction1/status/1022963512329596928>

It would have made sense to talk about the recommendations at the ASTDA meeting, but nothing.

From: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <tap1@cdc.gov>
Sent: Friday, August 31, 2018 10:13 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: RE: Good News!

Very. And, you will still be getting some hate mail.

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Friday, August 31, 2018 10:08 AM
To: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <tap1@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Good News!

Kind of sad how the intactivists have been able to shut this down.

From: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <tap1@cdc.gov>
Sent: Friday, August 31, 2018 10:00 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E] <peter.kilmarx@nih.gov>
Subject: RE: Good News!

Peter, 20 million cases later, but I guess there are still some folks getting HIV. Tom

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Thursday, August 30, 2018 3:45 PM
To: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <tap1@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: Good News!

Hi Tom,
Recommendations are finally out, 11 years after our Atlanta consultation -
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2788411/>

CDC male circumcision recommendations and background documents as well as the public and peer review comments and CDC responses were posted on the CDC DHAP website today and can be accessed via the following link: <https://www.cdc.gov/hiv/risk/male-circumcision.html>.

Not a lot of public communication planned.

Best,
PK

From: Dominguez, Ken (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 15 Oct 2015 14:45:12 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]; LeBaron, Charles (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP); Samandari, Taraz (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP); Mermin, Jonathan (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Published critique of Earp's attack on the draft CDC circumcision policy

Thanks Peter! Great article! Will be helpful in formulating our responses to public comments.

Ken

Kenneth L. Dominguez, MD, MPH
CAPT, U.S. Public Health Service
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
National Center for HIV, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Epidemiology Branch, Prevention for Negatives Team

From: Kilmarx, Peter (NIH/FIC) [E]
Sent: Wednesday, October 14, 2015 8:10 PM
To: LeBaron, Charles (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <cel3@cdc.gov>; Dominguez, Ken (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <kld0@cdc.gov>; Samandari, Taraz (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <tts0@cdc.gov>; Mermin, Jonathan (CDC/OID/NCHHSTP) <jhm7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Fw: Published critique of Earp's attack on the draft CDC circumcision policy

Nice supportive article. Good luck bringing this over the finish line.

Best to all.

Peter Kilmarx, MD, FACP, FISDA
Deputy Director, Fogarty International Center, NIH

From: Brian Morris <brian.morris@sydney.edu.au>
Sent: Wednesday, October 14, 2015 7:33 PM
To: Brian Morris
Subject: Published critique of Earp's attack on the draft CDC circumcision policy

Dear colleagues

You would be familiar with the ridiculous attacks mounted by intactivists and other anti-circs on good evidence-based male circumcision policies produced by the CDC and AAP in recent times.

These have been consistently repudiated by clinical, academic and other experts.

The URL below will take you to my critique of the published criticisms of the CDC draft recommendation by the well-known MC opponent, Brian Earp.

[http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fped.2015.00088/full?utm_source=Email_to_authors&utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers in Pediatrics&id=165120](http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fped.2015.00088/full?utm_source=Email_to_authors&utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers%20in%20Pediatrics&id=165120)

Open access, so free download.

Best wishes

Brian

Brian J. Morris, DSc PhD FAHA
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The University of Sydney
Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

The contents of this email might include material that could possibly reflect the expert views of an academic at the University of Sydney. Unless stated otherwise they should not be regarded as representing University policy since on many issues that academic staff are expert in the University does not maintain any specific policy.